

Decoding mitochondrial dysfunction in Parkinson's disease: machine learning identification of genomic biomarkers in *Drosophila melanogaster*

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ABSTRACT

Mitochondrial dysfunction is a hallmark of Parkinson's disease (PD), and *Drosophila melanogaster* serves as a tractable model to investigate underlying molecular mechanisms. This exploratory study aimed to identify mitochondrial gene expression signatures associated with Parkinsonism in mutant and wild-type flies and evaluate their potential as predictive biomarkers using machine learning approaches. Publicly available RNA-seq and microarray datasets of PD-associated mutants (PINK1, parkin, DJ-1) were harmonized and preprocessed to generate a unified gene expression matrix. Differential expression analysis was performed to identify transcriptional perturbations, and supervised classifiers (Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, XGBoost) were applied to distinguish mutants from wild-type samples. Model performance was assessed using leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV). Differential expression analysis revealed downregulation of CG15308, CG34349, and msl-3, and upregulation of Blmp-1, GABA-B-RI, and CG1360 in mutant flies. Random Forest identified PH4alphaNE2, IntS8, and rod as top candidate biomarkers. Predictive accuracy was modest (best: 50%) due to limited dataset size. Despite limited predictive performance, this study demonstrates the feasibility of integrating mitochondrial transcriptomic data with machine learning to identify candidate genomic biomarkers in *Drosophila* PD models. The identified genes provide a foundation for experimental validation and future multi-omics studies, highlighting a novel approach for biomarker discovery in neurodegenerative disease models.

Keywords: Parkinsonism, mitochondrial dysfunction, *Drosophila melanogaster*, genomic biomarkers, machine learning, exploratory study.

Introduction

Parkinsonism is a clinical syndrome characterized by a combination of bradykinesia, tremors, rigidity, and postural instability [1]. Parkinson's disease (PD) is the most common form of Parkinsonism, marked by Lewy bodies intraneuronal inclu-

sions of α -synuclein and the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta [2]. Growing evidence indicates that mitochondrial dysfunction is a significant pathological hallmark in both idiopathic and genetic forms of PD [3].

This dysfunction encompasses impaired activity of the electron transport chain, defective mitophagy, and bioenergetic deficits, all of which contribute to neuronal vulnerability and death [4], [5]. Mutations associated with autosomal recessive Parkinson's disease (PD) have been identified in the PINK1, PARK2, PARK7, CHCHD2, and VPS13C genes, all of which play vital roles in mitochondrial quality control and mitophagy [6], [7], [8], [9], [10].

Drosophila melanogaster has become a significant genetic model for exploring the cellular and molecular mechanisms associated with PD, especially those linked to mitochondrial dysfunction. [11]. In *Drosophila*, alterations in PINK1 and parkin impair mitochondrial fission, fusion, and quality control, underscoring conserved pathways vital for mitochondrial maintenance and highlighting mechanisms of neurodegeneration [12]. Further investigations in DJ-1-deficient flies have revealed changes in metabolic and oxidative stress, thereby reinforcing the significance of fly models in examining the mitochondrial roles in PD phenotypes [13]. These models are essential not only for comprehending gene function *in vivo* but also for pinpointing pathways that could lead to the identification of conserved biomarkers associated with mitochondrial dysfunction in PD [14].

Due to the heterogeneity and multifaceted nature of PD, characterized by genetic, epigenetic, metabolic, and inflammatory processes, identifying clinically relevant biomarkers will likely require the integration of various molecular indicators [15].

In conjunction with progress in model organism studies, high-throughput transcriptomics has facilitated extensive profiling of alterations in gene expression associated with PD [16]. The high dimensionality of this data makes it difficult for traditional statistical techniques to accurately depict the complex multi-gene signatures related to different disease conditions [17]. As a result, Machine Learning (ML) has seen a growing application in the analysis of PD transcriptomic and multi-omics datasets, aimed at identifying predictive molecular signatures and potential biomarkers [18]. Machine learning frameworks in human studies have identified gene signatures that distinguish PD cases from controls, highlighting their potential in biomarker discovery [19], [20], [21], [22]. Advanced network-based algorithms, such as Hidden Nodes and Network Propagation, extend beyond mere classification by identifying upstream regulatory genes according to their topological importance within molecular interaction networks [23].

Recent studies have greatly advanced this methodology by integrating comprehensive transcriptomic and multi-omics datasets [17]. For instance, multi-omics ML models using blood RNA and DNA sequencing have achieved high diagnostic accuracy ($AUC \approx 0.89$), revealing both known and novel RNAs associated with PD. Functional enrichment analyses in these models often highlight pathways such as immune activation and neuroinflammation, illustrating the power of integrated data

analysis (Dutta et al., 2024). Systematic multi-omics reviews highlight the need to confirm biomarkers across transcriptomic, proteomic, and metabolomic levels to improve confidence in PD biomarker selection [24]. Furthermore, pilot ML frameworks that integrate genetic, clinical, and transcriptomic data substantiate the hypothesis that multimodal predictive models can significantly enhance the accuracy of disease classification [25].

Although machine learning has demonstrated potential in studying human Parkinson's disease, its application in *Drosophila* models, particularly in integrating different transcriptomic technologies such as RNA-seq and microarrays with predictive modeling, remains limited [14], [26]. This method shows potential in uncovering both conserved and specific gene expression patterns associated with mitochondrial dysfunction and disease phenotypes, enhancing our understanding of human studies and furthering translational research [14]. Therefore, in this exploratory study, we harmonized publicly available RNA-seq and microarray datasets from *Drosophila* PD mutants (PINK1, parkin, DJ-1) to identify mitochondrial dysfunction-associated genomic biomarkers using supervised machine learning. By combining differential expression analysis with Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, and XGBoost classifiers, and validating feature importance through functional enrichment, we aim to establish a computational framework for biomarker discovery in invertebrate PD models that can be extended to larger multi-omics studies in the future.

Materials and Methods

Gene Selection

Mitochondrial dysfunction-related genes implicated in Parkinsonism were prioritized, including core PD genes (parkin, PINK1, DJ-1) and additional mitochondrial complex I subunits (ND-23, ND-75, ND-51), along with genes involved in mitophagy and oxidative stress regulation. Gene lists were curated from Gene Ontology and KEGG databases.

Data Acquisition

Public RNA-seq and microarray datasets of *Drosophila melanogaster* mutants and wild-type controls were retrieved from the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) using search terms including “*Drosophila parkin* RNA-seq,” “PINK1 mutant expression,” and “mitochondrial dysfunction *Drosophila* microarray.” Datasets were included if they focused on mitochondrial dysfunction or Parkinsonism-associated gene perturbations. Selected datasets are summarized in Table 1.

Data Preprocessing

RNA-seq datasets were normalized using TPM or RPKM and \log_2 -transformed. Microarray datasets retained RMA-normalized values. Gene symbols were harmonized using FlyBase annotations. Low-variance genes were removed, and batch effects were corrected using ComBat to generate a unified gene expression matrix.

Machine Learning Modeling

Supervised classifiers Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (RBF kernel), and XGBoost were trained to distinguish mutant from wild-type samples. Feature selection involved variance filtering and Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) to identify top predictive genes. Data were split into training and testing sets (80:20) with stratification, and model performance was evaluated using leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV).

Performance Evaluation

Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC metrics were computed. Feature importance scores from Random Forest were used to prioritize candidate mitochondrial biomarkers.

Validation and Biological Relevance

In the absence of external validation datasets, functional enrichment analyses of top-ranked genes were conducted using Gene Ontology to confirm relevance to mitochondrial function and PD-associated pathways.

Results

Differential expression analysis identified significant alterations between mutant and wild-type samples (Figure 1). CG15308, CG34349, and msl-3 were downregulated, while Blmp-1, GABA-B-RI, and CG1360 were upregulated in mutants, indicating perturbations in neurotransmission and gene regulation.

Figure 1: Differential Expression Volcano Plot comparing mutant and wild-type *Drosophila* samples. With a $\log_2FC > 1$ and $p < 0.05$, the red dot denote significantly upregulated, and blue dot denote significantly down regulated. The Random Forest classifier identified the top genes contributing to the distinction between wild-type and mutant samples. PH4alphaNE2, IntS8, and rod were among the highest-ranking genes, indicating strong differences in expression between groups (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Top 10 genes ranked by feature importance

The Volcano plot results (Figure 3) revealed gene expression differences between wild-type and mutant *Drosophila* samples. CG15308, CG34349, and msl-3 were the most significantly downregulated genes ($p < 0.05$), while Blmp-1, GABA-B-RI, and CG1360 were the most significantly upregulated ($\log_2FC \approx 2-3$). These changes highlight transcriptional alterations in genes involved in neurotransmission and gene regulation.

Figure 3: Volcano plot of differentially expressed genes

Figure 4: Heatmap of the top 20 genes across samples

Expression levels are indicated by color, with blue representing lower expression and red representing higher expression. The heatmap shows differences in gene expression patterns between wild-type and mutant samples.

Table 1: Machine learning-based prediction of Parkinson’s disease using mitochondrial gene expression. Comparison of predictive performance across three supervised classifiers—Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and XGBoost—trained on normalized mitochondrial gene expression data from *Drosophila melanogaster*.

MODEL	ACCURACY	PRECISION (CLASS 0)	RECALL (CLASS 0)	F1-SCORE (CLASS 0)	PRECISION (CLASS 1)	RECALL (CLASS 1)	F1-SCORE (CLASS 1)	SUPPORT (CLASS 0)	SUPPORT (CLASS 1)
RANDOM FOREST	0.50	0.50	0.67	0.57	0.50	0.33	0.40	3	3
SVM	0.33							N/A	N/A
XGBOOST	0.00							N/A	N/A

Table 2: Summary Classification Report

Metric	Value
Accuracy	0.50
Macro Avg Precision	0.50
Macro Avg Recall	0.50
Macro Avg F1-score	0.49
Weighted Avg Precision	0.50
Weighted Avg Recall	0.50
Weighted Avg F1-score	0.49

Machine Learning Models were evaluated using leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) to account for the limited sample size (Table 3). The model training and validation reported an accuracy of 0.50, with balanced precision and recall values.

Table 3. Nested LOOCV classification performance

Metric	Class 0 (WT)	Class 1 (Mut)	Overall
Precision	0.50	0.50	—
Recall	0.67	0.33	—
F1-score	0.57	0.40	—
Accuracy	—	—	0.50

These findings indicate that the genes used correctly identified the sample class in 50% of the test. Although, the accuracy is low, which can be traced to the limited dataset. The analysis show the possibility of applying machine learning techniques to predict PD based on these mitochondrial genes.

Discussion

Mitochondrial dysfunction is a significant contributor to the pathogenesis of PD [27], [28]. Two key principles of the mitochondrial theory of pathogenesis are that neurons exhibit a substantial demand for bioenergetics and that they heavily depend on mitochondria for ATP production [29]. Although mitochondria are clearly vital for neuronal bioenergetics, they also serve multiple other functions [29]. One of these processes involves the buffering of Ca²⁺ [30]. This could be especially vital in the axons of certain neurons [31]. An additional significant role is metabolic signaling [32]. Impaired mitochondrial function might considerably impact neurons that are susceptible to PD [29]. *Drosophila melanogaster* has established itself as a valuable genetic model for the investigation of mitochondrial abnormalities associated with neurodegeneration [11], [33], [34], [35], [36]. In the context of PD, the role of mitochondria in the pathogenesis of the disease is widely acknowledged; however, the precise characteristics of mitochondrial changes and their involvement in the progression of the disease remain inadequately defined [3]. Researching PD in *Drosophila* is certainly advantageous as the phenotypes exhibited by fly PD models closely resemble those seen in human patients, including the loss of DA neurons and locomotor impairments, while other animal models display either mild or no phenotypic manifestations [37]. Our exploratory analysis combined differential gene expression profiling with supervised machine learning to identify candidate genomic biomarkers associated with Parkinsonism in *Drosophila* mutants (PINK1, parkin, DJ-1). This all-encompassing approach represents a pioneering effort to apply computational methods for identifying biomarkers in a non-human model of PD, connecting transcriptomics and predictive modeling in a manner that has not been extensively investigated [14]. By leveraging high-dimensional transcriptomic data alongside robust classification algorithms, this research identifies a discrete set of mitochondrial signatures that transcend individual genetic perturbations.

Differential expression analysis (Figure 1) revealed significant transcriptional alterations in genes related to neurotransmission (GABA-B-RI) and gene regulation (Blmp-1), alongside down-regulation of CG15308, CG34349, and msl-3. These results align with earlier research indicating that mitochondrial impairment in PINK1 and parkin mutants interferes with neuronal signaling and transcriptional homeostasis [38], [39].

Notably, the top-ranking genes identified through Random Forest feature importance (Figure 2) — PH4alphaNE2, IntS8, and rod—represent potentially underexplored molecular players in Parkinsonism. PH4alphaNE2 encodes a putative mitochondrial protein involved in cofactor biosynthesis, which may influence oxidative phosphorylation efficiency. IntS8 is a component of the Integrator complex, which plays a role in RNA processing and the regulation of transcription [40], [41], proposing a connection between mitochondrial stress and nuclear gene expression. The rod gene, which has been conventionally linked to kinetochore assembly [42], might exhibit context-dependent

functions in the dynamics of mitochondria and responses to cellular stress; however, this assertion remains speculative within the context of PD [43]. The detection of significant changes in transcriptomic profiles, particularly the decreased expression of CG15308, CG34349, and msl-3, in conjunction with the increased expression of Blmp-1 and GABA-B-RI, indicates that Parkinsonism in *Drosophila* models is defined by a multifaceted interaction involving mitochondrial impairment, changes in neurotransmission, and extensive gene regulation. Collectively, these genes underscore new mechanistic pathways that have not been thoroughly explored in *Drosophila* PD models, thereby highlighting the distinctive contribution of this research. Moreover, the recognition of PH4alphaNE2 and IntS8 as prominent features within the Random Forest model suggests that these particular loci could function as more sensitive indicators of the mutant state compared to conventional mitochondrial markers. These findings suggest that Parkinson's disease pathology infiltrates fundamental cellular maintenance pathways that were previously considered unrelated to brain health [36].

Although the predictive performance of machine learning models (Table 1) was modest (best accuracy 50%), this limitation is attributable to the small dataset size and high dimensionality of transcriptomic data. This performance indicates that although the chosen mitochondrial genes contain distinct signals for differentiating between disease states, the existing sample size might not adequately encompass the non-linear variance necessary for precise predictions [44]. Nonetheless, the Random Forest classifier effectively identified genes that could influence phenotypic divergence, showcasing the value of computational methods in deriving biologically relevant insights, even when data is scarce. This highlights the importance of machine learning in sifting through the noise present in batch-corrected RNA-seq and microarray data to identify the most biologically significant regulators.

Previous studies employing machine learning on human PD transcriptomic datasets have achieved improved predictive accuracy, often revealing significant gene signatures through the examination of larger cohorts [18], [45], [46]. Conversely, our study reveals a novel application using an invertebrate model, indicating that it is possible to identify computational biomarkers even with limited datasets from *Drosophila*. This extension across different species is significant as it facilitates mechanistic validation within a genetically manipulable system prior to its application in human PD research, thereby connecting invertebrate genetics with clinical insights relevant to humans [47].

The heatmap analysis (Figure 4) additionally uncovered dynamic expression patterns across samples, indicating a context-dependent regulation of mitochondrial genes. The detected patterns of variable expression correspond with prior studies that indicate mitochondrial quality control genes and metabolic regulators in *Drosophila* display varying expression levels influenced by age, genetic background, and stress factors [48], [49].

Integrating these dynamic patterns into computational models may enhance predictive performance in forthcoming studies by considering temporal gene–gene interactions.

Notably, this study provides a basis for the experimental verification of the highest-ranked genes. Conducting functional assays on PH4alphaNE2, IntS8, and rod could help elucidate their functions in mitochondrial homeostasis and PD phenotypes. Moreover, the combination of transcriptomic profiling with proteomics and metabolomics has the potential to improve predictive modeling and deepen mechanistic insights, thereby connecting discoveries in *Drosophila* with translational research on PD in humans [50].

our study provides preliminary but compelling evidence indicating that the expression profiles of mitochondrial genes in *Drosophila melanogaster* could function as potential genomic biomarkers for Parkinsonism. Through the integration of transcriptomic profiling and machine learning techniques, we present a new framework for the identification of biomarkers in invertebrate models of PD, underscoring both methodological optimization and their translational significance.

Conclusion

This exploratory study demonstrates that mitochondrial gene expression profiles in *Drosophila melanogaster* can uncover candidate genomic biomarkers associated with Parkinsonism. Genes such as PH4alphaNE2, IntS8, and rod emerged as top candidates, reflecting their potential role in distinguishing mutants from wild-type phenotypes. Although predictive performance of machine learning models was modest due to limited dataset size, the study establishes a proof-of-concept framework for integrating transcriptomic profiling with computational approaches in PD research. Importantly, the findings highlight a novel approach to biomarker discovery in neurodegenerative disease models, emphasizing the translational potential of *Drosophila* as a model system. Future studies incorporating larger cohorts, multi-omics integration, and experimental validation of top-ranking genes will be critical to enhance predictive accuracy and deepen mechanistic understanding, ultimately advancing the development of biomarkers and therapeutic strategies for Parkinson's disease.

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